

Complexes of divalent cadmium with *N,N*-dimethyl-3-dibenzo[*b,e*]-oxepin-11-(6*H*)-ylidine-1-propanamine)chloride : synthesis and evaluation of thermal degradation kinetics

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A tricyclic antidepressant drug doxepin (C₁₉H₂₁NO), abbreviated as DOX, forms complexes with divalent cadmium metal of the type [Cd(DOX)₂X₂] (X = Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, Γ, 1/2SO₄²⁻ or CH₃COO⁻). In all the complexes, DOX coordinates through side-chain nitrogen atom. The TG data of degradation of the complex have been analyzed for kinetic and thermodynamic parameters employing Briodo's method.

Doxepin hydrochloride (DOX), chemically *N,N*-dimethyl-3-dibenzo[*b,e*]oxepin-11-(6*H*)-ylidine-1-propanamine) chloride is a tricyclic antidepressant with antianxiety and antihistamine properties¹. Its complexation behavior, biological studies and thermal decomposition kinetics towards Co^{II}^{2,3} and Pd^{II}³ have been reported recently. The present communication deals with the synthesis characterization, thermal decomposition and evaluation of kinetic parameters of bivalent cadmium complexes of doxepin.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses of the complexes indicate a metal-to-ligand stoichiometry of 1 : 2. Within the range of experimental error, elemental analyses of the compounds are as required by the chemical formulation. The complexes are non-hygroscopic, stable towards air and moisture. The conductivity value in 1 × 10⁻³ M solution show their non-electrolytic nature and also supports that the halides are within coordination sphere. All the complexes are diamagnetic in nature as expected for *d*¹⁰ configuration.

The IR spectrum of DOX-ligand showed a strong broad band at 2270–2500 cm⁻¹ (–N–CH₃) which disappeared in the spectrum of the Cd^{II} complexes, indicating participation of tertiary nitrogen attached to alkyl group combined with halogen⁴. The sharp ligand band at 1100 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C)⁵ appeared almost in the same region in the metal complexes, suggesting that the oxygen atom is not involved in bonding.

The participation of side-chain nitrogen was evidenced by the appearance of far-IR band at 425–445 cm⁻¹ (M–N)⁶.

The bands in the ligand and its complexes at 1190–1010 and 870–720 cm⁻¹ are due to C–H of-plane deformation and C–H out-of-plane deformation vibrations in the heterocyclic six-membered ring system. The spectra of all the complexes showed the absence of water molecule. Far-IR spectra of Cd^{II} chloride, bromide and iodide complexes registered medium band at 345 (M–Cl), 355 (M–Br) and 365 cm⁻¹ (M–I), respectively. The Cd^{II}-nitrate complexes exhibited three bands at *ca.* 1460, 1365 and 1046 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to *v*₄, *v*₁ and *v*₂ of coordinated nitrate ions which were not observed in the spectra of the ligand. Since the separation between *v*₄, *v*₁ ions is ~110 cm⁻¹, it is presumed that the nitrate ions are coordinated unidentately to Cd^{II} ion⁷. IR spectra of the acetato complexes showed bands at *ca.* 1606 and 1340 cm⁻¹ corresponding to *v*_u(CO₂) and *v*_s(CO₂⁻), respectively, indicating that the acetate group is unidentately coordinated to the metal ion⁸. The sulfato complexes showed four bands at *ca.* 1205, 1170, 1045 (overlapping with the ligand peak) and 985 cm⁻¹ corresponding to bidentate groups.

¹H NMR spectrum of DOX ligand showed signals at δ 2.3 (CH₂CH₂), 2.6–2.7 (–N–(CH₃)₂), –3.8 (C–H) and 7.0–7.5 (ArH). In the spectra of complexes, all the ligand signals remained at same position except the signals of –N–(CH₃)₂.

This shows the shift of alkyl protons attached to the tertiary nitrogen, thereby suggesting the involvement of tertiary nitrogen atoms in coordination with Cd^{II} ion. Thus the NMR data corroborate the IR data regarding the involvement of tertiary nitrogen atoms in bonding with Cd^{II} ion.

The reflectance spectra of all these complexes exhibited the weakest absorption band at 19600 cm^{-1} which are due to a charge transfer from d -orbital of the Cd^{II} metal ion to the π^* system of ligand⁹. These complexes also exhibited maximum intense band around 37000 cm^{-1} , ascribed to an intermolecular charge transfer transition within the ligand and which are assigned to $n\text{-}\pi^*$ transitions. The absence of $d\text{-}d$ bands in these complexes at longer wavelength is quite reasonable since the metal ions have filled d -subshells where $d\text{-}d$ transitions are highly forbidden¹⁰.

The thermograms were analyzed to give percentage weight-loss as a function temperature. Higher the values of temperature range (T_0 , T_{10} , T_{20} and T_{max}) higher will be the thermal stability¹¹. In the present complexes, more thermal stability has been found for Cd^{II} -iodide complex (228°). Least stability was for Cd^{II} -chloride (210°) complex which may be due to electronegative nature of the chloride ion. As far as the anion is concerned, the thermal stability of the complexes follows the order: Cl^- (210°) < Br^- (218°) < NO_3^- (223°) < CH_3COO^- (224°) < SO_4^{2-} (227°) < I^- (228°). The trend shows that the electronegativity/basicity of anions has strong effect on the thermal stability of the complexes¹². The integral procedure decomposition temperature values have significant importance due to the overall nature of the TG curves¹³.

The mass-loss occurring in the region $210\text{--}426^\circ$ is termed as first stage thermal degradation. In these steps, percent mass-loss is in the range $58.78\text{--}72.58\%$, which may be attributed to the decomposition of less thermally stable organic moiety. In the second stage of decomposition at $413\text{--}724^\circ$, the percent mass-loss in the range $10.49\text{--}26.39\%$ may be due to the loss of inorganic ligands. The experimental values of weight-loss are in good agreement with the weight calculated on the basis of stoichiometry proposed for the complexes. The final solid residue was cadmium oxide in all the cases in conformity with the percentage losses of mass obtained from TG curves.

The kinetic parameters were calculated using Broido's method¹⁴. The complexes showed low activation energies ($20.18\text{--}31.40\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) in the first stage while high in the second stage degradation ($100.08\text{--}121.12\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). The thermodynamic functions for all the complexes were evaluated for both the stages of degradation. The enthalpy values in the range $15.18\text{--}113.92\text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ for all the steps of com-

plexes compared to those of T_0 ($210\text{--}228^\circ$) show that with the decrease in enthalpy, the decomposition temperature also decreases¹⁵.

Experimental

All the chemicals and solvent used were of A.R. grade. DOX (Intas Pharmaceutical) was used.

An ethanolic solution (4 mmol) of DOX was added to a solution of $\text{CdX}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2.5 mmol) (where $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , $1/2\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ or I^- and $n = 1, 2, 3$) with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 8 h. The solid complexes formed were washed with cold ethanol, then with ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator over fused CaCl_2 . The Cd^{II} sulfato complexes were prepared by heating the mixture on a water-bath ($75\text{--}80^\circ$) for 1 h. The acetato complexes were synthesized in aqueous media.

Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy balance using $[\text{Hg}(\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4)]$ as calibrant at 305 K. An Equipronics EQ-DCM-P conductivity meter was used for measuring molar conductance in $1 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ solution at room temperature. The reflectance spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP₈₋₁₀₀ spectrophotometer using MgO as reflectance standard, IR spectra (KBr) on a Hitachi 297 spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) on a Jeol (60 MHz) spectrometer relative to internal TMS at room temperature. Cd was determined by EDTA method. Elemental analyses were carried out at Department of Chemical Technology, University of Bombay, Mumbai. The molecular weight was determined by Rast's method.

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Note

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